

Eisenmenger Syndrome: A Gestational Menace**Ashok Kumar Devoor¹, Ashok Kumar HS², Neha G Yalagachin³, N Venkatesh⁴**¹Unit Chief, Associate Professor Department of OBG, Vani Vilas Hospital, BMCRI, K. R. Road, Bengaluru, Karnataka²Assistant Professor, Department of OBG, Vani Vilas Hospital, BMCRI, K. R. Road, Bengaluru, Karnataka³Senior Resident, Department of OBG, Vani Vilas Hospital, BMCRI, K. R. Road, Bengaluru, Karnataka⁴Junior Resident, Department of OBG, Vani Vilas Hospital, BMCRI, K. R. Road, Bengaluru

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Abstract:**Background:** Cardiac disease is a major cause of maternal mortality after PPH and eclampsia. Undiagnosed left to right shunt over a long duration causes development of pulmonary artery hypertension leading to reversal of the shunt. This process of Eisenmengerisation is a cause for cardiac failure and death.**Methodology:** The study conducted over one year at Vani Vilas hospital, Bengaluru. All the women who were newly diagnosed with Eisenmenger syndrome were considered into the study. Their details, mode of presentation, mode of termination, gestational age at presentation, pulmonary artery hypertension and maternal outcomes was documented and analysed.**Result:** Seven cases of newly diagnosed Eisenmenger syndrome were admitted. The mean age was 23.16 years. The mean gestational age at presentation was 30+4 weeks. The maximum pulmonary artery pressure was 88mm Hg. 100% maternal mortality was noted.**Keywords:** Eisenmenger Syndrome, Cardiac Disease, Maternal Mortality.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Eisenmenger syndrome is the end result in which the unrepaired, unobstructed left to right shunt lesions of the cardia turn to right to left shunt leading to hypoxia and cardiac failure [1]. It represents the severe end of the spectrum of congenital heart diseases when pulmonary artery hypertension develops. It is defined by systemic-to-pulmonary shunting of blood through any large congenital cardiac defects at any location that permits increased pulmonary blood flow which later progresses into severe elevation of pulmonary vascular resistance (PVR) resulting in reversal (pulmonary-to-systemic) or bidirectional shunting [2]

The process of eisenmengarisation can develop at any shunt lesions – ASD, VSD, PDA, truncus arteriosus and PDA in which the pressures in the pulmonary circulation overcome the systemic circulation, leading to the reversal of flows. The physiological changes of pregnancy affect the cardia in multiple ways. From the increasing preload and decreasing afterload, the systemic resistance gradually reduces in pregnancy. Adding to this if there's preexisting Eisenmenger syndrome, then the rate of decompensation of the maternal cardia increases rapidly, as the reversal of

shunt increases. The post tricuspid shunts decompensate more rapidly than pre-tricuspid shunts [3]. It leads to a plethora of multi system failure that cannot be compensated by the body, leading to morbidity and mortality. The incidence of ES in pregnancy is less than 3% with mortality ranging from 20% to 50% [6].

First described by Victor Eisenmenger in the 19th century [4], the various terminologies associated with this disease complex include – Eisenmenger syndrome, Eisenmenger complex, Eisenmenger reaction, overt Eisenmenger syndrome. The last one implying a multisystem failure- including hepatic, renal, immunologic, neurological and orthopaedic manifestations. [5]

Despite the health facilities available for early diagnosis and treatment of congenital heart diseases, due to various reasons, the facilities are not availed by the people leading to undiagnosed, untreated shunt lesions which progress to the level of Eisenmenger complex. This study aims to highlight the importance of undiagnosed ES, which present for the first time in pregnancy leading to maternal morbidity and mortality.

Aims and Objectives

1. To describe the presentation of newly diagnosed Eisenmengers syndrome in pregnancy
2. To describe the severity of pulmonary artery hypertension and the gestational age of presentation.

Materials and Methods

Type of study: Observational study.

Duration: 1 year.

Location: Vani Vilas Hospital, BMCRI, Bangalore.

Inclusion Criteria

- Newly diagnosed Eisenmenger’s syndrome cases admitted in OBG ICU at Vani Vilas Hospital.

Exclusion Criteria

- Age less than 18 years.
- Age more than 40 years.
- No consent.
- Previously diagnosed Eisenmenger’s disease.

The antenatal women who are newly diagnosed with Eisenmenger’s syndrome and admitted at the

hospital are considered into the study. Their details noted and the data is entered into Microsoft excel sheet and analysed in terms of age of the patient, gestational age at presentation, the mode of presentation of the disease, the mode of termination of pregnancy, the maternal and fetal outcomes.

Results

7 antenatal cases of newly diagnosed Eisenmenger syndrome were admitted at the OBG ICU in Vani Vilas hospital over a period of one year. The mean age of presentation was 23.16 years. All the women presented with the chief complaints of breathlessness and orthopnoea with signs of cardiac failure. Pulmonary edema was a common finding.

The average gestational age at presentation was 30+4 weeks. The diagnosis was made on 2D echocardiography. The women were all nulliparous and were on ventilator from the time of admission. The mode of termination of pregnancy was by lower segment caesarean section or by hysterotomy in all the women under general anaesthesia. Post-operative deaths occurred from day 1 to day 3 of surgery. All the seven cases ended in maternal mortality. The mean pulmonary artery pressure was 75.14mm Hg (minimum – 68mm Hg, maximum-88mm Hg).

Figure 1: Age distribution

Table 1: Gestational Age At Presentation (Weeks) and Pulmonary Arterial Pressure (mm of Hg) at different age groups

Sl. No.	Age (Years)	Gestational Age At Presentation (Weeks)	Pulmonary Arterial Pressure (mm of Hg)
1	20	28	68
2	22	27+5	72
3	23	29+5	68
4	24	32+2	78
5	24	34	82
6	24	34+5	88
7	26	29+3	70

Figure 2: Gestational age at presentation

Discussion

A study by Yang Liu et al [6], described 42 patients with ES. The mean age of the patients was 26.7 years. 40 of the cases underwent caesarean delivery (95.2%) and 11 maternal mortalities were reported. Death was mainly related to pulmonary hypertensive crisis and heart failure. Shinde SS et al described a case of ES in pregnancy [7] in which the patient presented with complaints of breathlessness and findings of cardiac failure. Multidisciplinary approach was followed and patient was medically managed on sildenafil and furosemide oral medications. Caesarean delivery was done at 35 weeks under epidural anaesthesia in view of breech in labour. Her 2d echocardiography revealed ostium secundum with a pulmonary artery pressure of 155mm Hg. Fetal growth lag by 12 weeks was also noticed.

Alsomali et al [8] described a case report of a G2P1L0 with ES (secondary to ASD with PAH), was on medical management. Despite being advised termination of pregnancy in the first trimester, she continued with the pregnancy and underwent a LSCS at 33 weeks under epidural anaesthesia to deliver healthy baby and had a good postoperative outcome.

Conclusion

Undiagnosed ES, presenting first time in pregnancy is a diagnostic conundrum. With poor maternal outcomes, ES is still a contraindication for pregnancy. But if diagnosed late, needs a multidisciplinary approach with poor maternal and fetal outcomes (with some exceptions). So early detection of cardiac disease is the key for management.

This research work was approved by Ethical committee of Vani Vilas Hospital, BMCRI, K.R Road, Bengaluru, Karnataka 560002

References

1. Lopez BM, Malhamé I, Davies LK, Velez JM, Marelli A, Rabai F. Eisenmenger syndrome in pregnancy: a management conundrum. *Journal of cardiothoracic and vascular anesthesia*. 2020 Oct 1; 34(10):2813-22.
2. Borges V. T. M., Magalhães C. G., Martins A. M. V. C., and Matsubara B. B., Eisenmenger syndrome in pregnancy, *Arquivos Brasileiros de Cardiologia*. 2008; 90: e39–e40, <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0066-782x2008000500015>, 2-s2.0-44849142219, 18516394.
3. Heath D, Edwards JE. The pathology of hypertensive pulmonary vascular disease; a description of six grades of structural changes in the pulmonary arteries with special reference to congenital cardiac septal defects. *Circulation*. 1958; 18: 533-547. 1958/10/01.
4. Eisenmenger V. Die angeborenen Defekte der Kammerscheidewand. *Z Klin Med*. 1897; 32:1-28.
5. Chaix MA, Gatzoulis MA, Diller GP, et al. Eisenmenger Syndrome: A Multisystem Disorder-Do Not Destabilize the Balanced but Fragile Physiology. *Can J Cardiol*. 2019; 35:16 64-74. 10.1016/j.cjca.2019.10.002
6. Hong S, Kang X, Lio KU, Le Y, Wang C, Lin J, Zhang N. Multidisciplinary approach for the management of term pregnancy complicated by Eisenmenger syndrome. *Journal of Zhejiang University-SCIENCE B*. 2023 Jan; 24(1):89-93.
7. Shinde SS, Khade SA, Kamble S, et al. Pregnancy with Eisenmenger's Syndrome. *J South*

- Asian Feder Obst Gynae. 2022; 14(6):753–754.
8. Alsomali F, Mushtaq S, Bakir M, Almustanyir S. Fruitful Pregnancy Outcome in a Case of Eisenmenger Syndrome With Severe Pulmo-

nary Hypertension: A Rare Case Report. Cureus. 2022 Jan 10; 14(1):e21068. doi: 10.7759/cureus.21068. PMID: 35155027; PMCID: PMC8825312.